

An Open Problem in Matching Sets of 3D Lines*

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Abstract

Methods for matching sets of 3D lines depend on whether line lengths are finite or infinite. In terms of line lengths, three basic cases arise in matching sets of lines: (1) finite to finite, (2) finite to infinite, and (3) infinite to infinite. For cases 1 and 2, which have not been treated in the literature, we present convergent iterative algorithms that (almost) always find the best match. For case 3, Faugeras and Hebert (FH) [3] have proposed a popular iterative method that cannot be guaranteed to converge. We present an alternative approach that does converge. However, we also show that neither the FH solution, nor our solution is invariant with respect to coordinate transforms, which renders any best match meaningless. Thus, a satisfactory solution to case 3 does not yet exist. We discuss the underlying problem, which is the representation of infinite lines, and suggest alternatives that may lead to an invariant solution.

1 Introduction

A basic tool in computer vision is matching geometric features such as points, lines, surfaces, etc. This has applications in scene registration, object localization and recognition, pose estimation, motion estimation, and others. In this paper we discuss matching two sets of corresponding 3D line segments. The line sets may be extracted from a model and an image, or from two images. We refer to one set of lines as the model and the other set as the image. We want to find the rigid transformation (translation and rotation) that gives the best match of the image with the model.

Lines in models and images are line segments with finite lengths. However, while we can always reliably extract the line direction from the image (otherwise we do not have a line), under noisy conditions we may not be able to obtain the line segment length with the desired accuracy. In cases where we are able to accurately detect the line segment length, then we have a

finite-length line segment which has as usable information the line location, direction, and length. Otherwise we have an infinite line that has as usable data only the line location and direction.

In this paper we assume that we have already detected the lines, or line segments, and hypothesized the corresponding lines in the model and the image. We should make two remarks. First, detection of 3D lines, or line segments, is a nontrivial problem in early vision, which we do not address here (see [4]). Second, often a challenging aspect of problems in computer vision is determining the correspondences. Certain pairings of features in the image and model can be eliminated by geometric constraints, e.g. the rigidity constraint, all others have to be examined based on the goodness of match [4]. Indeed, the matching algorithms we present here may be used to verify hypothesized correspondences rapidly and reliably. Since we can have infinitely long lines or finite-length line segments, we may encounter the following three basic cases in line matching: (1) line segments in both model and image are finite; (2) line segments in model are finite, while image lines are infinite; (3) model and image lines are both infinite. Mixed cases, where some line segment lengths are known and others are not, can be handled by combining these three cases. Fig. 1, for example, illustrates case 1, where the model and its edges, as well as, certain edge fragments detected in the image are shown.

Cases 1 and 2 have not been discussed in the literature. In this paper, we present an iterative, convergent method that almost always finds the best match. We note that Zhang and Faugeras [11] use line lengths only to rule out corresponding line hypotheses, but not in the matching algorithm.

Case 3 is treated by Faugeras and Hebert [3], where they propose an iterative method for its solution which is not guaranteed to converge. Here, we present an alternative approach that is guaranteed to converge. However, more importantly, we show that neither method is invariant to the translation of the co-

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Figure 1: A polyhedral object and its edges (top row). A 3D edge image (lower left), and its best match to the model (lower right)—image is shown by thick lines.

ordinate system. This non-invariance to coordinate transforms makes the *best match* rather meaningless. Hence, case 3, which may have the widest applications, is an open problem.

The line matching problem has received considerable attention. Related papers include the following. Ref. [7] discusses matching equal length 3D line segments. Refs [5][7][9] discuss matching 3D curves, or polygonal arcs. Matching a set of points to a curve without knowing the correspondences is addressed in [1][10].

In matching lines (or other extended, non-point-like features) we have to simultaneously determine the coordinate transform, as well as the corresponding line parts. That is, even after we hypothesize corresponding pairs of lines, we still have to find the corresponding parts in each line pair. This problem of matching corresponding lines with *unequal lengths* turns out to be a nonlinear optimization problem, which we solve with a convergent, iterative technique. The line matching algorithms we present here are built upon a closed-form solution for matching sets of corresponding line segments with *equal-lengths* that appeared recently in the literature [5][7]. Therefore, we begin by briefly discussing that solution.

The method we present in this paper, as well as those cited above, are based on regression. The Hough transform (evidence accumulation) approach has also been used for 3D line matching, e.g. [2].

2 Equal-Length Line Segments

The best match between two sets of 3D lines, where corresponding pairs have equal lengths can be calculated in closed-form. Here we briefly discuss the solu-

tion and refer to [7] for details.

Consider two sets of (directed) line segments: the model set $A = \{A_n\}$, and the image set $X = \{X_n\}$, where $n = 1 \dots N$ and A_n and X_n are a pair of corresponding line segments with the same lengths. We represent the line segment A_n with its center point \mathbf{a}_n , the unit vector along its direction $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_n$, and its length l_n , i.e. $A_n = (\mathbf{a}_n, \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n, l_n)$. Similarly $X_n = (\mathbf{x}_n, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n, l_n)$. The transformation $\mathcal{T} = (\mathbf{t}, R)$ that operates on X is given by:

$$\mathcal{T}\mathbf{x}_n = \mathbf{t} + R\mathbf{x}_n, \quad \mathcal{T}\hat{\mathbf{y}}_n = R\hat{\mathbf{y}}_n, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{t} and R are the translation vector and rotation matrix. The distance measure, $M(A, \mathcal{T}X)$, between the two sets is defined as the sum of Euclidean distance squares of corresponding pairs:

$$M(A, \mathcal{T}X) = \sum_{n=1}^N [l_n \|\mathbf{a}_n - \mathbf{t} - R\mathbf{x}_n\|^2 + l_n^3 (1 - \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n^\top R\hat{\mathbf{y}}_n)/6]. \quad (2)$$

Vectors are column matrices, $\|\mathbf{a}_n\|$ is the length of \mathbf{a}_n , and \top denotes matrix transpose. The minimum distance measure, $M^* = \min_{\mathcal{T}} M(A, \mathcal{T}X)$, is called the *mismatch measure*. The advantage of this distance measure is that the transformation minimizing it can be found in closed-form.

First the rotation matrix R is computed in closed-form, using the quaternion representation [3][6], from the 3×3 cross-covariance matrix S ,

$$S = \sum_{n=1}^N [l_n(\mathbf{a}_n - \bar{\mathbf{a}})(\mathbf{x}_n - \bar{\mathbf{x}})^\top + l_n^3 \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n^\top / 12], \quad (3)$$

and then translation $\mathbf{t} = \bar{\mathbf{a}} - R\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is calculated. Here

$$\bar{\mathbf{a}} = \sum_{n=1}^N w_n \mathbf{a}_n, \quad \bar{\mathbf{x}} = \sum_{n=1}^N w_n \mathbf{x}_n, \quad w_n = l_n / \sum_{n=1}^N l_n.$$

3 Unequal-Length Line Segments

We formulate the problem of matching sets of 3D line segments (or lines) as matching sets of corresponding lines with *unequal lengths*. This provides a unified approach to solving the three cases we mentioned in the Introduction. While the equal-length case is a 6-variable optimization problem, the unequal-length matching is a $(N+6)$ -variable problem—6 for rotation and translation, and N for overlapping portions.

3.1 Finite Model, Finite Image (FMFI)

Suppose we have two sets of line segments where the corresponding lines have unequal lengths. Again let $A = \{A_n\}$ and $X = \{X_n\}$, be the model and image

sets, where $A_n = (\mathbf{a}_n, \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n, L_n)$ and $X_n = (\mathbf{x}_n, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n, l_n)$. To keep notations simple in this paper we assume $L_n \geq l_n$. The general case, without this constraint, is treated in [8].

In this problem, when we fit the image to the model we have to find, in addition to how to rotate and translate the image, the portion of A_n that corresponds to X_n . We denote the point on A_n that corresponds to \mathbf{x}_n by $\mathbf{a}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n$, where $\{s_n\}$ are the *shift* parameters that must be found. The distance measure is obtained from (2) by substituting $\mathbf{a}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n$ for \mathbf{a}_n :

$$M(A, \mathcal{T}X) = \sum_{n=1}^N [l_n \|\mathbf{a}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n - \mathbf{t} - R\mathbf{x}_n\|^2 + l_n^3 (1 - \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n^\top R \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n) / 6]. \quad (4)$$

We want to minimize the distance measure with respect to \mathbf{t} , R , and the set of shift parameters $\{s_n\}$. By solving the equations $\partial M / \partial s_n = 0$, we find the shift parameters

$$s_n = (\mathbf{t} + R\mathbf{x}_n - \mathbf{a}_n)^\top \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n, \quad (5)$$

subject to the constraint $|s_n| \leq (L_n - l_n) / 2$, in terms of \mathbf{t} and R . Note that for a given \mathbf{t} and R the s_n given in (5) minimizes (not maximizes) $M(A, \mathcal{T}X)$. This can be verified easily by showing that all the eigenvalues of the $N \times N$ Hessian matrix of M are positive: the Hessian is diagonal with elements $\partial^2 M / \partial s_n \partial s_m = 2\mathcal{L} \delta_{nm}$ where $\mathcal{L} = \sum_n l_n > 0$. Also, note that $\mathbf{a}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n$ with s_n given in (5) is the closest point of line segment A_n to point \mathbf{x}_n . This justifies the tentative correspondence assumption in [1] for matching points to an object.

It can be shown that the minimization problem, unlike the equal-length case, cannot be reduced to a linear form in R , hence a closed-form solution cannot be found. However, we can solve the problem with an iterative optimization method described below.

Note that if the shift parameters, $\{s_n\}$, are known then the corresponding portions of line segments in set A are specified and this problem reduces to the simpler problem of matching sets of corresponding line segments with equal length for which a closed-form solution exists. When s_n is given, the point $\mathbf{a}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n$ on line segment A_n corresponds to the center of line segment X_n . Thus, if we replace \mathbf{a}_n with $\mathbf{a}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n$ everywhere in Sec. 2, i.e. match line segments $(\mathbf{a}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n, \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n, l_n)$ and $X_n = (\mathbf{x}_n, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n, l_n)$, then we may compute \mathbf{t} and R . Having calculated \mathbf{t} and R , then the values of $\{s_n\}$ can be improved according to (7). Therefore, we propose the following iterative algorithm for finding the best match between two sets of line segments with unequal length.

1. Initialize the set $\{s_n\}$.
2. Replace \mathbf{a}_n by $\mathbf{a}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n$ and compute the cross-covariance matrix from (3). Then compute rotation R and translation \mathbf{t} .
3. Update the set $\{s_n\}$ according to (5). Go to step 2, and repeat until all s_n converge.

The proof that the algorithm converges is straightforward. For given values of $\{s_n\}$, the rotation and translation reduce the value of the distance measure (actually minimize the distance measure); and updating the values of $\{s_n\}$ for the given rotation and translation further reduces the value of the distance measure (actually minimizes the distance measure). Since the distance measure is bounded from below, $M(A, X) \geq 0$, then the algorithm must converge after a number of iterations.

Based on extensive empirical results (Sec. 4), we find that the algorithm almost always converges to the global minimum, no matter how it is initialized. The number of iterations depends on the problem at hand and the desired accuracy. We find the algorithm converges rapidly requiring only several iterations.

3.2 Finite Model, Infinite Image (FMII)

In this case line segments in the model are finite, while in the image they are infinite. This case arises when exact information about the model exists, while the image may be noisy so that line segment lengths cannot be detected with sufficient confidence, hence, only the image line directions are usable. For ease of notation, we interchangeably use the names of model and image and treat the model as infinite. Thus, an image line segment is represented as before by its midpoint, direction and length, $X_n = (\mathbf{x}_n, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n, l_n)$, while a model line is represented by $A_n = (\mathbf{a}_n, \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n)$, where $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_n$ is its direction and \mathbf{a}_n is its closest point to the coordinate system origin, which implies $\mathbf{a}_n^\top \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n = 0$.

The distance measure between line set A and line segment set X is identical to (4). The s_n is also identical to (5) but without the constraint because $L_n = \infty$. The algorithm for finding the best match is also identical to the iterative algorithm given for FMFI.

3.3 Infinite Model, Infinite Image (IMII)

In this case both model and image line segments are infinitely long. This problem arises when information about line segment lengths is either unavailable or cannot be extracted, and thus only line directions are usable. This is the case discussed by Faugeras and Hebert [3].

We treat this case as matching a set of infinitely long line segments and a set of finite line segments that have the same length l because all lines must make the same contribution (l is arbitrarily long). We

represent the model lines by $A_n = (\mathbf{a}_n, \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n)$, where $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_n$ is its direction and \mathbf{a}_n is its closest point to the coordinate system origin, i.e. $\mathbf{a}_n^\top \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n = 0$. The image line segments are represented by $X_n = (\mathbf{x}_n, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n, l)$, where l is its length, $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_n$ its direction and \mathbf{x}_n is its closest point to the coordinate system origin, i.e. $\mathbf{x}_n^\top \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n = 0$. The corresponding point to \mathbf{a}_n is $\mathbf{x}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n$ which is the midpoint of the virtual line segment of length l . Parameters s_n are unknown and have to be determined. The distance measure between the two sets is

$$M(A, \mathcal{TX}) = \sum_{n=1}^N [l \|\mathbf{a}_n - \mathbf{t} - R(\mathbf{x}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n)\|^2 + l^3 (1 - \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n^\top R \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n) / 6]. \quad (6)$$

The solutions of $\partial M / \partial s_n = 0$ are

$$s_n = (\mathbf{a}_n - \mathbf{t})^\top R \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n. \quad (7)$$

This $M(A, \mathcal{TX})$ can be minimized by a similar algorithm to that given in Sec. 3.1, with obvious modifications:

1. Initialize the set $\{s_n\}$.
2. Replace \mathbf{x}_n by $\mathbf{x}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n$ and compute the cross-covariance matrix from (3), then compute rotation R and translation \mathbf{t} .
3. Update the set $\{s_n\}$ according to (7). Go to step 2, and repeat until all s_n converge.

3.3.1 FH Formulation

The problem we solve above is not the exact problem that Faugeras and Hebert (FH) [3] want to solve. In their formulation the transformed point $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_n = \mathcal{T}(\mathbf{x}_n + s_n \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n)$ must be the closest point to the origin, that is $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_n^\top R \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n = 0$. This constraint yields

$$s_n = -\mathbf{t}^\top R \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n. \quad (8)$$

The constraints for FH formulation, Eq. (8), and for ours, Eq. (7), become identical when $\mathbf{a}_n^\top R \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n = 0$. This is true for non-noisy cases since $R \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n = \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n$, and is satisfied approximately for moderately noisy data. For high noise data, as well as for cases with incorrect line correspondences, where matching becomes meaningless, the FH constraint is not satisfied well. The following quantity

$$\Delta s = \sum_{n=1}^N |\mathbf{a}_n^\top R \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n| / \sum_{n=1}^N \|\mathbf{a}_n\|, \quad (9)$$

is a good measure of the goodness of agreement with the FH solution. In noise-free cases $\Delta s = 0$.

Faugeras and Hebert [3] propose an iterative solution, which is non-convergent and requires a good starting transformation. The algorithm we presented here is convergent and appears to be independent of initialization. If one wishes to use the FH formulation, we suggest using our convergent algorithm to find a good starting match and then solve the FH formulation by a downhill simplex search. The FH formulation introduces two weight factors, K_1 and K_2 , respectively for the direction-dependent part of the distance measure (2nd term in (6)), and the location-dependent part (1st term in (6)). The virtual length l in our formulation is related to the ratio of the weights according to $l = (6K_1/K_2)^{1/2}$.

3.3.2 Best Matches Are Non-invariant

The FH and our formulations have a drawback in common: Neither is invariant to the choice of the coordinate system origin. This is illustrated in Fig. 2. In this 2D example, the model consists of two vertical and one horizontal lines. The image is made by rotating 30° the model's right vertical line. As can be seen, changing the coordinate system origin changes the best match of the image to the model. Fig. 2 shows the result of the best match for our formulation. FH also behaves similarly.

The FH formulation is not invariant because it matches the distances of corresponding lines from the origin, which are not *intrinsic* properties of the line sets. A change of the origin changes the distances and hence the best match. Our formulation is not invariant because the selected line segments in the image are arbitrary. (Here we select them relative to the origin, but, in general, they may be chosen arbitrarily.) Changes in the selected line segments change the best match. Note that a small perturbation in the translation vector, $\mathbf{t} \rightarrow \mathbf{t} + \delta \mathbf{t}$ where $\|\delta \mathbf{t}\| \ll \|\mathbf{t}\|$, induces identical perturbations in the shift parameters,

$$\delta s_n = -\delta \mathbf{t}^\top R \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n + O(\|\delta \mathbf{t}\|^2),$$

in both formulations up to the first order in the perturbation. This indicates that both formulations suffer to the same degree from non-invariance.

We have also experimented with a modified distance measure, where each distance-dependent term is scaled by the model line distance from the origin. Although, it reduces the dependence on the choice of the origin, it does not entirely circumvent the problem. Note that when the model and image are identical both formulations become invariant to the choice of the origin. However, as the similarity of model and

Figure 2: Changing the coordinate system origin changes the best match in the IMII case. Solid lines are the model, dotted lines the image, and the origin is the black dot.

image degrades, the best match becomes more sensitive to the location of the origin.

3.3.3 Alternative Formulations

The underlying cause of non-invariance of the best match in either formulation is in the representation of lines. In these formulations, line locations are given with respect to the coordinate system origin. This representation, which depends on a point external to the line set, does not remain invariant under a coordinate change. To overcome this problem, we have to represent line locations with respect to a reference point that is fixed with respect to the line set. Even though this point can, in principle, be arbitrary, the reference points \mathbf{p}_A and \mathbf{p}_X for sets A and X must be corresponding points. However, we do not know beforehand the corresponding points, which are indeed what we set out to find (simultaneously with the best transformation). The reference point that appears to be the best choice (and the correct choice when the image and model are not noisy) is the point that is overall closest to all the lines, that is, the point that minimizes the sum of the distances from all lines in the set:

$$\mathbf{p}_A = \arg \min_{\mathbf{p}} \sum_n \text{dist}(\mathbf{p}, A_n).$$

An alternative approach that does not rely on a single reference point is to find the best match through minimizing the sum of the distances between the closest points on corresponding line pairs, that is,

$$M(A, \mathcal{T}X) = \sum_n [l \|\mathbf{a}_n - \mathcal{T}\mathbf{x}_n\|^2 + l^3 (1 - \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n^T R \hat{\mathbf{y}}_n) / 6],$$

where l is an arbitrary length specifying the relative importance of directional and locational matches.

Here \mathbf{a}_n and $\mathcal{T}\mathbf{x}_n$ are the closest points of approach on lines A_n and X_n . Note that \mathbf{a}_n is no longer a fixed point, but changes as X_n changes direction and location. We are investigating these two alternatives in terms of convergence, reliability, and sensitivity to noise.

4 Tests

We have extensively tested the performance of the line matching algorithms, with simulated and real data sets. We present some results here and refer to [8] for more extensive experiments and mixed cases.

We generated hundreds of simulated data sets with varying degrees of noise for selected values of $N = 10, 20, 50, 100, 200$. For each N , we ran the FMFI algorithm on the data sets several thousand times with different random initializations. All runs converged to the best solution (with the exception of $N = 10$, for which less than 0.1% of the runs converged to a non-optimal match). The number of iterations depends on the problem and the desired accuracy for convergence of shift parameters. With a stringent convergence criterion of 10^{-3} length-unit, the number of iterations ranged between 5 and 20. FMII and IMII algorithms were similarly tested. Results were similar, in that the algorithm converged to the same solution in each example, and that convergence was fast.

For the example shown in Fig. 1, there are $N = 18$ edge fragments in the image. We used the FMFI algorithm with 1000 different initial configurations. The algorithm converged to the same solution in all the trials, within 5 to 10 iterations with the convergence criterion of $\epsilon = 10^{-3}$ length-unit. For $\epsilon = 10^{-4}$ the iterations ranged between 8 and 14, and for $\epsilon = 10^{-5}$ the algorithm converged in 11 to 18 iterations.

We also include a test example that demonstrates the application of the line matching technique. We use the data obtained by an underwater imaging sonar (UIS), which operates in a manner similar to volume-imaging ladars. The UIS ensonifies the scene and collects the backscatter energy as a function of distance, thus yielding a 3D grey level image. Fig. 3 shows the photograph of a flat, non-uniform grid of thin steel bars used to test the resolution of the UIS, and the side view of a volume-rendered acoustic image of the grid placed in a water tank.

The steel grid is modeled by 24 line segments (12 horizontal and 12 vertical) with known lengths, all lying in the same plane. From the 3D volumetric image, we were able to reliably extract 6 horizontal and 7 vertical bars and estimate their lengths. Thus, we used the FMFI algorithm with $N = 13$. Fig. 4 shows the best match of the image (solid lines) to the model

Figure 3: Photograph of the grid, and a view of its 3D underwater acoustic image.

(dotted lines) when the line correspondences are identified correctly. The mismatch measure is $M^* = 4$. Also shown are the best matches when corresponding lines are misidentified by one row ($M^* = 92$), by one column ($M^* = 141$), and by one row and one column ($M^* = 231$). This example also demonstrates that the resulting mismatch measure, M^* , from the line matching algorithm may be used for correspondence verification. In each case, we ran the algorithm with several thousand different initializations. All runs converged to the same result. The number of iterations ranged from 4 to 17. Note that even though the grid is a flat planar object, its acoustic image is 3D and the extracted line segments are slightly non-coplanar. In Fig. 4, we show only the 2D top view. Also note that the algorithms are valid in matching 2D lines.

5 Discussion

We presented a solution to the problems of matching two sets of line segments (case 1), and matching a set of line segments to a set of infinite lines (case 2). The iterative solution converges rapidly and (almost) always finds the best match.

We discussed the problem of matching two sets of infinite lines (case 3) and showed that the non-convergent solution of Faugeras and Hebert [3] proposed in 1986, as well as the convergent solution presented here, are both non-invariant to the choice of the coordinate system origin. This renders the best match meaningless. Thus, a satisfactory solution to matching sets of infinite lines remains open.

Figure 4: Results of matching the grid image (solid lines) to the model (dotted lines): with correct correspondences (top left), and with correspondences off by 1 row, 1 column, and 1 row and 1 column.

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